

ADVANTAGES OF USING AN ELECTRIC CAR

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Recently, President Shavkat Mirziyoyev made a speech at the second international summit "Green growth and cooperation for global goals - 2030" (P4G) held in the Republic of Korea. In it, the head of our state said: "Today, we should not ignore the warning call that Mother Nature is sending to us. Unfortunately, climate change is getting worse. In Central Asia, where we live, the average annual temperature has risen by about one degree in the last 30 years. The decline of major river basins and biodiversity in our region is a serious concern. Evaporation-increasing gases and large-scale atmospheric pollution are exacerbating the problem.

Today, no one doubts that the efforts of countries should be more active and effective in order to achieve the goals of "green development". We have no other option," he said. To fulfill this task, it is necessary to work in new directions based on the further development of the economy related to the production and service sectors while preserving the resources necessary for human life and health, the environment and ecology.

Uzbekistan is entering the era of electric cars. Today, the car that brings people closer to their destination is more developed and includes many conveniences. What are the conveniences of electric cars, which are becoming more and more interesting every day?

An electric car is a vehicle powered by one or more electric motors, powered by an independent energy source rather than internal combustion. It is designed to be easy to use, with a separate transmission, lightweight chassis and body, and replaceable batteries.

Electric cars were imported into Uzbekistan in 2018

Taking into account the usefulness of electric cars not only for driver comfort, but also for ecology and environment protection, a number of incentives and benefits have been systematically created in order to popularize them in Uzbekistan.

We can list the following benefits:

1. a base for the production of electric cars and their main components in an experimental method will be established and their main components will be produced;
2. the fee for the purchase of new electric cars manufactured in the republic, as well as the disposal fee for electric cars (including car kits) will be canceled;
3. the network of charging stations for electric cars will be further developed.

Electric cars differ from other vehicles equipped with internal combustion engines in the following ways:

1. the low cost of electric cars compared to conventional cars;
2. almost does not make a sound when moving;
3. expensive, bulky gearbox will not be needed;
4. does not consume engine oil;
5. an electric car can use regenerative braking to recharge its electronic battery;
6. Dampers of electricity generators can also be used for recharging.

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Electric cars are environmentally friendly, since they have an electric engine instead of a combustion engine, they do not emit toxic air, carbon dioxide, and allow to save liquid fuel. It takes in air from the outside only for conditioning purposes.

Fresh air enters the car cabin through a filter. Noiseless movement, no need to heat up before driving - are considered as its additional conveniences. For some who wish, it has an artificial sounding device. Cost-effectiveness is the same thing for us Uzbeks.

Machine maintenance and spare parts are also a bit of a problem. This is also related to the fact that electric cars are becoming more popular in our country than in other countries. Therefore, it is not wrong to call it a temporary problem.

Currently, approximately 70 percent of the machines have spare parts, and 30 percent are ordered as needed. They are usually non-perishable, non-trivial parts. Older models can be found, but newer or some modified car parts are a little harder to find. In these cases, they are ordered and brought by air.

Concerned about the world's ecology and economy, and in order to partially contribute to its future improvement, the world is gradually moving away from cars running on internal combustion engines to fully electric cars powered by electricity.

According to statistics, 58% (1.4 million tons) of the total harmful waste emitted into the atmosphere in Uzbekistan is accounted for by automobile transport, and in Tashkent, this figure is much higher - 93% (397 thousand tons), we read in the newspapers.

So, how to solve the existing painful problem in cities where the number of industrial and household waste and traffic is increasing day by day? What measures should be taken? A series of questions about how to keep the air of our yard and neighborhood clean are being answered one after another.

When the answers to the questions are found, it is natural for us to realize that it is necessary for us all to work together to find a solution to the resulting headache, not just one or two people.

So, in the green economy, it is necessary to act while ensuring the harmonious and sustainable development of people, nature and the economy. Just because I do one thing, another thing is not lost. For example, trees are not ruthlessly cut down to build houses, increasing technologies is not carried out at the cost of filling the atmosphere with poisonous gases, etc. Achieving sustainable development in this way is one of today's global issues.

REFERENCES:

1. Kh.R. Gaffarov., A.Kh. Samandarov. Prospects for the application of "green economy" technologies in the automotive industry (electric cars).
2. H.R. Gaffarov, M. Tokhirov. Quality control of the main field works. International scientific journal: "Young scientist" Kazan 2017. No. 5 (part I). P.31-34.